

Potentiometric Studies of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Lanthanum(III) and Thorium(IV) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid and Ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid as Primary Ligands

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Formation Constants of mixed ligand complexes of lanthanum(III) and thorium(IV) with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as primary ligands, and anthranilic acid (ANA) as secondary ligand have been investigated potentiometrically. The values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ have been found in the order $\log K_{MAL}^{NTA} < \log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$. The trends in stability constants of ternary complexes with respect to metal ion have been found in the order $La^{III} > Th^{IV}$.

RECENTLY there has been considerable interest in the study of the mixed ligand systems by *pH*-metric method¹⁻⁴. In continuation of our earlier work⁵⁻⁷ on the application of Irving-Rossotti titration technique⁸ for the study of ternary complexes, the results obtained on the study of systems MAL, where $M=La^{III}$ or Th^{IV} , A =nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) or ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), and L =anthranilic acid (ANA) are presented in this paper. The formation constants K_{MAL}^{MA} have been determined at 30° and at ionic strength, $\mu=0.2 M$ (KNO_3). The modified form of Irving and Rossotti technique was used.

Experimental

For determining the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes K_{MAL}^{MA} the following four mixtures were prepared in four different titration vessels and then titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution using a *pH* meter.

- (i) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid.
- (ii) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ anthranilic acid.
- (iii) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand solution + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution.
- (iv) $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ nitric acid + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ primary ligand + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal solution + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ anthranilic acid solution.

The mixtures were prepared in such a way that the concentration of common ingredient were identical in different mixtures. An appropriate amount of neutral sodium nitrate solution was added to each mixture to maintain the ionic strength at $\mu=0.2 M$ and the volume of each mixture was adjusted to 100 ml by adding double-distilled water. In each

case the ratio between metal (M), primary ligand (A) and secondary ligand (L), *i.e.* $M:A:L$, was kept 1:1:1. The four mixtures were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide solution (1.096 M) using *pH* meter, observing all usual precautions. The four titration curves obtained are referred as (A) acid titration curve, (B) secondary ligand titration curve, (C) primary complex titration curve and (D) ternary complex titration curve.

Results

In the case of the mixed ligand systems presented in this paper, primary ligands (A), EDTA and NTA form very stable 1:1 complex with La^{III} and Th^{IV} ion and the observations of primary complex curves indicate that the complete formation of 1:1 complex (MA) takes place at very low *pH* 4.0 in the range where secondary ligand (L) could not get attached with the binary complex (MA). Only after the complete formation of MA , can the secondary ligand (L) combine with it to give the ternary complex (MAL).

In the present work the value of protonation stability constant of ANA was not determined because of the titrations are to be carried out at very low *pH*. And it is not required for the calculation of $\bar{n}$ and *pL* values. The value of 'practical' proton ligand stability constant of ANA was determined ($\log K^H=3.64$) and was used in the calculation of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$.

Stability constants of mixed ligand complexes: It is observed from the curve (C) that MA is formed at low *pH*. Horizontal distances between curves indicate that MAL formation takes place only after the complete formation of 1:1 MA complex. In this range hydroxo complex formation does not

take place. The difference, $V_3 - V_2$ corresponds to the amount of secondary ligand which gets bonded with MA and so $\bar{n}$ and pL can be calculated using the same equation as in original paper⁸. The values obtained for $\log K_{MAL}^A$ by the method of interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values are presented in Table 1. In separate experiments the possibility of formation of complexes, such as MA_2L and MAL_2 has been completely ruled out.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES
 $\mu = 0.2 M$

Sl. no.	Complex	Constant	At 30°
1.	La^{III} -NTA-ANA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.60
2.	La^{III} -EDTA-ANA	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	4.22
3.	Th^{IV} -NTA-ANA	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.20
4.	Th^{IV} -EDTA-ANA	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	3.28

Discussion

The stability constant of 1 : 1 complexes of NTA and EDTA with La^{III} and Th^{IV} are reported to have high values. Hence, possibility of substitution reaction is completely ruled out and formation of mixed ligand complex is certain. The formation of ternary chelates M-EDTA-ANA can easily be explained on the basis of the assumption that the

coordination sphere of M expands to occupy the secondary ligand.

It is interesting to observe the trend in the values of mixed ligand complex formation constants $\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$ and K_{MAL}^{EDTA} for both La^{III} and Th^{IV} ions. The values for EDTA ternary chelates are found to be higher than that of the corresponding NTA ternary chelates. This is understandable, since in the case of EDTA complexes the coordination number of metal becomes eight so stabilising the chelate. In view of the above discussion, it is considered that the effective coordination number of La^{III} and Th^{IV} ions is eight in these ternary systems. The values of mixed ligand complex stability constants for Th^{IV} are found to be lower than the corresponding La^{III} complexes. The effective ionic radii of La^{III} is greater than Th^{IV} because of which La^{III} favours expansion of coordination sphere and forms more stable ternary complexes.

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